

Herso circular woodworks

Circular furniture and interiors without waste

Recovered wood material is remanufactured into beautiful designs for furniture, floors and interiors that have a unique character and valorise the vivid nature of wood surfaces and colours in long-lived products.

Highlights of innovative features

- With an own collection network, the company recovers wood supply from municipal waste and recycling centres.
- Clients can choose from design patterns that are created through assembly of different recovered wood origins.
- 'No waste' is used as brand for floors and interior walls, which are a reuse option also for demolition waste wood.
- Products are already labelled 'FSC Recycled' and an Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for architects is being developed.
- Versatile products which value respect for natural resources.

Recovered wood that is manufactured into valuable products revalorizes the natural material wood. Durable quality furniture is one of the best options to prolong the carbon storage of materials that are usually discarded. Circular brands by SMEs help to raise public awareness for the Circular Economy.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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